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Talent Management Research Trends in International Market-Based Organizations: A Bibliometric Analysis from 2018 to 2021

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to collect information on previous research on talent research trends in international market-based organizations 2018 - 2021, with Bibliometric analysis. The analytical tool used in this article is to use VOSviewer. The data sources used are 985 RIS documents obtained from Google Scholar and Scopus databases with Publish or Perish software. The analysis results show that the most significant nodes are firm performance. This shows the trend of talent management that is most often carried out. These nodes also correlate with a performance measure and culture nodes.

Keywords: Talent Management, Bibliometric Analysis, Firm Performance, International Organization, Trend Research

1. Introduction

Globalization is changing how business works and creating a new era in almost all industrial sectors. This certainly impacts the increasingly complex market complexity in the business world, the evolution of technology in the future, and a significant increase in global competition (Tarigan et al., 2018). Issues related to globalization that occur require every organization in all fields to face competitiveness in their respective industries. In this competition, talent management today is the fundamental driving force for organizations to succeed in facing globalization (A El Dahshan et al., 2018). In addition, due to changing industry dynamics, organizational managers in all sectors need a new perspective on the work goals and attributes of future generations of workers to attract, recruit and retain talented people (Qureshi et al., 2022). Therefore, every organization needs continuous learning

to obtain further information that can be used as a competitive advantage and develop an effective business strategy. This causes the need for organizational learning processes to increase.

Talent management is crucial in creating, developing, and maintaining a competitive advantage for every organization (Jindal & Shaikh, 2021). In the face of globalization, organizations must be responsive to organizational learning that focuses on individuals involved in the organization because they are a source of ideas and knowledge in line with how to design appropriate strategies for employees to compete in the international market. The strategy applied must be correct so that the organization can run following the specified goals. Organizations must also have characteristics, develop and, as long as possible, retain employees, especially those with extraordinary potential. Therefore, organizations compete with each other to acquire and retain talent so that their organizations develop and continue to grow (A El Dahshan et al., 2018).

Human capital refers to knowledge, skills, and abilities more valuable to the recipient organization than current organizations (Amankwah-Amoah, 2020). Additionally, businesses that are able to recruit and keep competent or great workers through efficient talent management will be able to thrive in a changing business climate since these workers may be able to grow and advance in ways that are advantageous to the firm. That way, talent management is indeed very influential in this issue. *Talent management* is a strategic process that is very important in ensuring the sustainability and success of an organization (Shingenge et al., 2022). A competent workforce is currently being prioritized more as a result of advancements in the information economy. The key to getting the best outcomes is having the best talent. A winning organization is created through an efficient talent management system that uses tactics designed at various levels. The competitive advantage of a winning organization depends on the ability to effectively recruit, retain, deploy and engage talent at all levels of the hierarchy (Hongal & Kinange, 2020a).

Talent management is also a major global challenge facing most organizations worldwide. Due to the scarcity of talent, organizations worldwide are competing for the same talent to acquire and retain talent to sustain their operations and continue to grow in service and profitability. Since 2010, there has been an increasing number of empirical studies on talent management, leading to the first claim that this mode of management, as the concept mentioned earlier, is likely to become a mature trend in the next few years (TABOR-BŁAŻEWICZ, 2019). Thus, it can be explained that talent management is important to study in line with the development of international-based business organizations. Companies such as AT&T Inc., Walmart Inc., JP Morgan Chase & Co., and Accenture PLC have begun efforts to prepare workers for new roles. At a time of historically low unemployment and rapid digital transformation requiring high-tech job skills, more US companies are saying they want to help their employees transition to new positions (Chip Cutter, 2019).

2. Method

This research was conducted to collect information from previous research related to trends in talent research in international market-based organizations from 2018 - 2021 so that it is included in Bibliometric research. Bibliometric methodologies summarize the application of quantitative techniques (i.e., bibliometric analysis—e.g., citation analysis) to bibliometric data (e.g., publication units and citations) (Donthu et al., 2021) To conduct a literature review, meta-analysis, bibliometric study, and content analysis. This study adopted a method to identify, sort, and report related articles (Nagariya et al., 2021).

The review of criteria that might be integrated in the selection and recruiting process for company growth has been explored in several earlier papers on the issue of talent management and bibliometric models (Abbasi et al., 2022). The previous research discussed more about the condition of talent management itself on a global scale (Beechler & Woodward, 2009). In the meanwhile, a different piece explores how talent management affects organizational performance (Hongal & Kinange, 2020b), (Ejovwokeoghene et al., 2018), (A El Dahshan et al., 2018). Some of these articles became support for the preparation of this research trend.

The data sources for this research are international articles, and the organization of the data is done by searching through the database that we got through Google Scholar on the publish or perish software. For keywords in the search field it is written as (JUDUL-ABS-KEY ((TALENT MANAGEMENT INTERNATIONAL MARKET-BASED ORGANIZATIONS "all"))). The open access and registry institution keywords or phrases are searched in the database using the "Document Search" search area. The year of publication, the organization that published it, the country, the name of the journal/publication, the type of text, and the research subject were all analyzed descriptively with a maximum limit of 1000 documents. From these keywords, we got 985 documents which we made the main research material. The second database used to get data is Scopus, where the search field is written as follows: TITLE-ABS-KEY(talent management international market based organizations) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2018)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ECON")) only 6 RIS data were obtained.

To find out the results of the literature analysis in terms of the quantity of documents each year, the activeness of the authors on this topic, and countries with dominant references. Meanwhile, for data retrieval through Scopus with the following keywords: TITLE-ABS-KEY(talent management international market based organizations) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2018)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ECON"))

Data is exported in RIS Export file format to distribute research map information. The researcher then exported the data in (RIS) format and used VOSviewer. Data analysis using VOSviewer application to display bibliometric maps (Prastya et al., 2021) from a research design that focuses on the main themes of research problems in international market-based organizations 2018 - 2021. Based on this description, the following is the research model of this article:

Figure 1: Research Model

3. Results

3.1 Statistics

If we look more deeply, bibliometric research from 2018 to 2021 continues to increase yearly. This figure also represents the publication trend of bibliometric papers between 2018 and 2021. The data is taken from the Scopus database using the keyword "bibliom*". So looking at the data, researchers or writers still favor the trend of analysis using the bibliometric method.

Figure 2: Documents by year

Source: Scopus data analysis

From the graph results, seen from the graph results continue to increase from 2018 to 2021, it can be explained that research using bibliometric analysis schemes is still exciting and favored by some researchers. Bibliometrics in that year was quite popular because this database is usually used in academic research and bibliometric analysis due to its large size, the number of indexed papers and journals, and high scientific relevance. (Almeida et al., 2021).

Year ↓	Documents ↑
2021	5593
2020	3886
2019	2840
2018	2261

Figure 3: Documents by year

Source: Scopus data analysis

More specific results can be seen in the table above, where based on the results of the analysis obtained from the Scopus database, the research related to the bibliometric model in 2018 was 2261 studies, followed by the following year as many as 2840 in 2019 and 2020 as many as 3886 documents. The most documents from the results of the Scopus database analysis are in 2021 with a total of 5593 research documents. The increase in the number of documents each year indirectly explains that researchers increasingly favor research with bibliometric models. The increase in the number of documents with bibliometric models could also be because based on bibliometric techniques researchers can also identify different sub-fields, and characterize them concerning their underlying assumptions, research design, contributions to the field and future research trajectories. (Anand et al., 2021). Additionally, some studies have stated that quantitative review methods, such as bibliometric analysis, can give researchers a high degree of completeness without a time or scope restriction and minimize worries about selection bias in the sampling process (Zhang et al., 2021).

Documents by subject area

Figure 4: Documents by subject area

Source: Scopus data analysis

Other results from the analyses produced by Scopus from 2018 to 2021, the subject areas of research with a fairly large percentage are economics, econometrics and finance and engineering (13.2%) and engineering with the same percentage (13.2 %). The next subject area, which is related to social science articles, is (23.7%). The largest subject area is business, management and accounting (31.6%). The number of studies that focus on the subject area is certainly in line with the sector experiencing growth. Growth in this sector can be caused by various factors.

Growth also describes a company's overall increase in resources (including cash and human capital), output (including the quantity of items produced), and market share (Kalogiannidis, 2021). Expansion to acquire new markets is essential to increase profitability. However, of course, this process must be accompanied by good management. In this regard, a study found that employee performance, selection, and recruitment procedures play an essential role in business growth (Abbasi et al., 2022). The largest percentage is another consideration that the trend of talent management is a topic that can be studied more deeply.

Documents by country or territory

Compare the document counts for up to 15 countries/territories.

Figure 5: Documents by country or territory

Source: Scopus data analysis

Talent management is not always related to how managers set strategies for their employees to improve company performance but also in efforts to retain employees. Therefore, how to secure and retain key talent emerges as a management problem for managers (Yi et al., 2021). In line with this opinion, another study of trend TM explains Talent Management is the process of attracting, finding, growing, attracting, retaining, and placing people who are invaluable to the company, considering the “good prospects” for the long term or as they perform the function. - an important function for a company (Suwaidi et al., 2018).

4.2 Competition

Firm performance is then connected to the competition nodes. Competition in globalized talent management is changing how business works and creating a new era in almost all industrial sectors. This leads to a sharp rise in global competitiveness, ongoing technological advancements, and the complexity of the expanding industry that are altering the corporate landscape (Tarigan et al., 2018). Issues related to globalization that occur require every organization in all fields to face competitiveness in their respective industries. In this competition, talent management today is the fundamental driving force for organizations to successfully face globalization (A El Dahshan et al., 2018). In addition, due to the changing industry dynamics, organizational managers in all sectors need new perspectives on the work goals and attributes of future generations of workers to attract, recruit and retain talented people (Qureshi et al., 2022).

The increasingly fierce competition also encourages organizations to have a competitive advantage. Talent management plays a crucial role in creating, developing, and maintaining a competitive advantage for any organization (Jindal & Shaikh, 2021). In the face of globalization, organizations must be responsive to organizational learning that focuses on individuals involved in the organization because they are a source of ideas and knowledge in line with how to design appropriate strategies for employees to compete in the international market. The strategy must be correct so the organization can run following the specified goals and have a competitive advantage.

4.3 Director

The next trend of discussion related to talent management is the director or leader. Additionally, the capacity of the company to successfully attract, hold on to, use, and engage talent at all levels of the hierarchy is its competitive edge (Hongal & Kinange, 2020b). It also explains that in addition to employees with talents, leaders are also involved in achieving organizational goals and competitive advantage. A leader is someone who organizes and plans every operational activity, and he has the right to provide something according to the needs of his organization (Abdulridha Jabbar & Hussein, 2017).

Leaders can empower employees and encourage them to feel responsible for realizing the vision and mission of the organization (Putri & Rofi, 2018). In other words, not only looking for employees who match the organization, but the leader must also nurture his followers to bring out the best performance in the organization. That way, talent management will be integrated with the leadership style. Some things that must be considered by companies for their employees are by providing training to support employees in the development process in carrying out work, paying attention to the talents or talents possessed by these employees to achieve success in the company and how the leadership style of the company leaders to assist employees in implementing his work in the field.

4.4 Performance Measure

The next trend is towards performance measures. Considering that employees with good talent scores are so important for organizations and companies, previous research stated that “there are three dimensions in talent management as a measurement tool which includes Talent Attraction which must be appropriately planned to get transparent results from overall results and the development of consistency organization, Talent Development with benefits in increasing the output of what has been learned, and the last is Talent Retention which is the primary concern of the company to maintain a competitive workforce (Sari et al., 2020). Additionally, according to other research, most firms place a high priority on attaining performance targets, which they do so by employing key performance indicators to measure progress. This strategy is related to management by objectives, where superiors

and subordinates agree on job assignments and responsibilities for a certain period of time, specify precise goals, evaluate these goals, and establish a deadline (Boštjančič & Slana, 2018). Trends related to performance measures according to bibliometric results do not have much interest, so it can be an opportunity in the future for further research.

4.5 Culture

Nodes from the firm performance are also correlated with several topics, one of which is culture. Some researchers put forward the idea of possible differences in TM practice depending on the cultural context but admit that too little empirical research has been done so far (Forsman et al., 2018). In another study, TM is not a foreign practice in culture. On the contrary, it can be used as a helpful tool for employee attraction, retention, development, and improving organizational performance in a highly competitive environment (Ejoywokeoghene et al., 2018). The study explains that the topic of culture has a relationship with firm performance. TM strategy in the organization is not all created by the organization.

As for organizations that adopt the TM strategy from organizations in developed countries to be implemented, even adopt it in its entirety. However, some researchers have argued that organizations in developing nations shouldn't just follow the TM models used in developed nations because they might not produce the same results because of a variety of issues (like as cultural differences, structural inequalities, conflicts that arise from differences in culture and religion, and underdeveloped financial markets), which will have an impact on how effectively it is implemented (Aina & Atan, 2020). In line with the results of bibliometric analysis, research related to TM and culture can be developed and further research conducted in the future.

5. Conclusion

This research is an analysis of trends from previous research. Using bibliometric analysis to get research trends with the VOSviewer tool and Publish or Perish to collect data from Google Scholar and SCOPUS databases. The database is then compared based on the specified keywords. From the google scholar database, the amount of data obtained was 985 RIS data, while the SCOPUS database only had 6 RIS data. In the end, no further calculations were carried out due to insufficient data. The selection of keywords that are carried out can also affect the search results that have been carried out so that the lack of data obtained cannot be ascertained due to the lack of publications in the database, but because keywords determine the search for the two databases.

Based on the results of research on RIS data from the Google Scholar database assisted by publishing or perish with the VOSviewer analysis tool, the trend of TM in international market-based organizations has the most significant nodes, namely "firm performance." This indicates that most TM research is related to the topic, namely firm performance. In line with this trend, several studies explain that the goal of talent management is to create a high-performing and sustainable organization that meets its strategic and operational goals and objectives (A El Dahshan et al., 2018). And organizational performance depends on the performance of its employees. If an organization's employees have unique competencies, it will differentiate them from their competitors (Hongal & Kinange, 2020a). There are other nodes related to firm performance trends, namely competition, director performance measure, and culture.

Some of these trends are the result of research that has been done on the primary subject of talent management, with the most important node being "firm performance," where most firms place a high priority on reaching performance objectives, which they evaluate using key performance indicators. This strategy is related to management by objectives, where superiors and subordinates agree on job assignments and responsibilities for a certain period of time, specify precise goals, evaluate these goals, and establish a deadline (Boštjančič & Slana, 2018) as well as the idea of possible differences in TM practice depending on the cultural context, but acknowledges that too little empirical research has been done so far (Forsman et al., 2018).

Acknowledgments

This research is an analysis of trends that are spread over 2018 – 2021. This research is only limited to discussing research trends and does not discuss in detail the results of the analysis that has been done. From the results of this trend, future researchers can develop research in terms of nodes that have received less attention from researchers but are pretty important. Node talented manager is one of them. These nodes are considered necessary because the most critical role in talent development is played by operational managers (direct managers). These are managers who need to understand what makes each employee stronger (Ahmadiyeh et al., 2020). By developing research based on nodes not paid attention to, it is hoped that the analysis and research will be more varied and can explore more details in the research conducted.

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